

Phase transfer catalyst mediated one-pot synthesis of 4-hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin

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The synthesis of two new 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins under phase transfer catalyst conditions is described.

We report herein the synthesis of 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins using *o*-hydroxy benzoic ester and phenyl acetyl chlorides in acetone-potassium carbonate medium in presence of phase transfer catalyst, benzyltriethyl ammonium chloride (TEBAC). Earlier we reported their one-pot synthesis without the aid of PTC¹.

Four different 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins (**1a-d**) were synthesized of which two (**1c** and **1d**) have not been reported earlier. It was found in this attempt for process improvement, the time of synthesis of the coumarins was considerably reduced. Also the synthesis of coumarins (**1c** and **1d**), which could not be achieved by the same method without using PTC, was possible by this method using PTC.

- 1a** R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
1b R₁ = OMe, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
1c R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
1d R₁ = OMe, R₂ = R₃ = H, R₄ = NO₂

Experimental

3-Aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins (1). General procedure :

A mixture of *o*-hydroxy benzoic ester (1 mmol) and freshly prepared aryl acetic acid chloride (1.2 mmol) as re-

fluxed in acetone-potassium carbonate medium in presence of benzyltriethylammonium chloride for the time mentioned. After the completion of the reaction, TLC was noted and the mixture was filtered. The solvent was evaporated from the filtrate and the residue treated with water. The unreacted ester was removed by extraction with ether and aqueous solution was acidified with dilute HCl (1 : 1) to yield the product, which was crystallized from ethanol.

A co-IR was recorded with authentic sample of the 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins (**1a** and **1b**).

Coumarins **1c** and **1d** were characterized by recording PMR spectrum of their acetates.

4-Hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin (1a) : A mixture of methyl salicylate (1 ml) and phenyl acetyl chloride (1.5 ml) in presence of PTC was refluxed for 10 h to yield the product : γ_{\max} 3056 (OH), 1673 cm⁻¹ (lactone CO). co-IR was recorded with available authentic sample.

4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3-phenylcoumarin (1b) : A mixture of methyl 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoate (540 mg) and phenyl acetyl chloride (1 ml) in presence of TEBAC was refluxed for 10 h to yield the product : γ_{\max} 3422 (OH), 1651 cm⁻¹ (lactone CO). co-IR was recorded with available authentic sample.

4-Hydroxy-3-(4-nitrophenyl)coumarin (1c) : A mixture of methyl salicylate (1 ml) and *p*-nitrophenyl acetyl chloride (2 ml) in presence of PTC was refluxed for 15 h to yield the product : γ_{\max} 3125 (OH), 1695 cm⁻¹ (lactone CO); δ (ppm) 6.3–6.7 (4H, m), 7.0–7.5 (4H, m), 2.1 (s, acetyl).

4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3-(4-nitrophenyl)coumarin (1d) : A mixture of methyl 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoate (540 mg) and *p*-nitrophenyl acetyl chloride (1.5 ml) in presence of PTC was refluxed for 10 h to yield the product : γ_{\max} 3422 (OH), 1651 cm⁻¹ (lactone CO); δ (ppm) 6.6–6.9 (3H, m), 7.0–7.5 (4H, m), 2.4 (s, acetyl).

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